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Review Article

**GERIATRIC SYNDROMES: SYSTEMATIC
LITERATURE REVIEW.**

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Abstract:

This review is aiming to discuss the geriatric syndromes, the presented review was conducted by searching in Medline, Embase, Web of Science, Science Direct, BMJ journal and Google Scholar for, researches, review articles and reports, published over the past years. were searched up to November 2018 for published and unpublished studies and without language restrictions, if several studies had similar findings, we randomly selected one or two to avoid repetitive results. On the basis of findings and results this review found urinary incontinence, injurious falls, functional impairment, frailty, sensory impairment, depression, cognitive impairment, significant worsening of existing syndromes at admission and discharge, and association between the common geriatric syndromes and predefined adverse outcomes of hospitalization.

Keywords: geriatric syndromes, chronic disease, HIV, diabetes

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INTRODUCTION:

Geriatric syndromes are defined as multifactorial conditions that result from deficits in multiple domains including clinical, psychosocial and environmental vulnerabilities.^{1,2} Geriatric syndromes are a fundamental construct in gerontology that provide evidence of aging and predict clinically important outcomes such as healthcare utilization and mortality.^{3,4}

Studies investigating the prevalence of geriatric syndromes in general medical inpatients have mainly focused on single syndromes.^{5,6} One small study examined the presence of more than one syndrome (mobility, toileting, grooming, transfer, feeding, bladder or bowel incontinence, and mental status) in 71 medical patients aged 74 and older 2 weeks before admission, on Day 2 of hospitalization, at discharge, and 1 week after discharge.⁷ No recent studies have quantified the presence of multiple geriatric syndromes in a single cohort of medical patients. Rockwood *et al.*⁸ pointed out that conceptual models of multiple syndromes are useful for developing geriatric medicine, arguing that studies quantifying the presence of a number of syndromes are as important as those examining the types of syndromes. A good understanding of the prevalence and incidence of an array of geriatric syndromes would facilitate more precise clinical care.⁹ The current article reports on the prevalence and incidence of geriatric syndromes from a prospective observational study, designed primarily to identify predictive factors for in-hospital acquisition of geriatric syndromes.¹⁰

Another important approach to diabetes in the elderly is the assessment, prevention and treatment of geriatric syndrome. The so-called “geriatric syndrome” refers to multifactorial health conditions that occur when the accumulated effects on multiple systems render an old person vulnerable to situational changes.¹¹ One of the most serious geriatric symptoms is functional disability. Cross-sectional studies in the USA showed that diabetes was associated with a twofold increased risk of being unable to perform daily physical tasks.^{12,13}

Older adults with multimorbidity, or co-occurrence of multiple chronic diseases, have poorer self-rated health and functional status, greater utilization of health care, and potentially earlier mortality than older adults with single diseases.¹⁴ Multi morbidity is common in the older adult population. It has been reported that 65% of Medicare beneficiaries have two or more chronic diseases and 43% have three or

more;¹⁵ other studies have found that more than 50% of older adults have multimorbidity.^{16,17} Furthermore, having newly reported chronic diseases has been associated with risk of functional dependency.¹⁸ The research reported in this article adds to the study of multi-morbidity by examining the co-occurrence of chronic diseases with geriatric syndromes. Geriatric syndromes, such as falls and urinary incontinence (UI), are conditions that have not traditionally been considered to be chronic diseases; nonetheless, geriatric syndromes have been shown to be as prevalent as chronic diseases and to be associated with functional dependency in older adults.¹⁹

RESULTS:

Eleven thousand one hundred thirteen adults, representing 37.1 million Americans aged 65 and older, were interviewed. Forty-five percent were aged 76 and older, 58% were female, 8% were African American, and 4% resided in a nursing home. Respondents with more conditions were older and more likely to be female, single, and residing in a nursing home (all $P < 0.001$). Fifty-six percent had at least one of the five index conditions, and 23% had two or more. Of respondents with one condition, 20% to 55% (depending on the index condition) had two or more additional conditions.²⁰

The most frequently reported premorbid syndromes were bladder incontinence (44%), impairment in any activity of daily living (ADL) (42%). A high proportion (42%) experienced at least one fall in the 90 days before admission. Two-thirds of the participants experienced between one and five syndromes (cognitive impairment, dependence in any ADL item, bladder and bowel incontinence, pressure ulcer) before, at admission, and at discharge. A majority experienced one or two syndromes during the premorbid (49.4%), admission (57.0%), or discharge (49.0%) assessment period. The syndromes with a higher incidence of significant worsening at discharge (out of the proportion with the syndrome present premorbidly) were ADL limitation (33%), cognitive impairment (9%), and bladder incontinence (8%). Of the syndromes examined at discharge, a higher proportion of patients experienced the following new syndromes at discharge (absent premorbidly): ADL limitation (22%); and bladder incontinence (13%).²¹

We studied 155 participants with a median age of 57 (IQR 54-62); (94%) were men. Pre-frailty (56%), difficulty with instrumental activities of daily living (46%), and cognitive impairment (47%) were the most frequent geriatric syndromes. Lower CD4 nadir (IRR 1.16, 95% CI 1.06-1.26), non-white race (IRR

1.38, 95% CI 1.10-1.74), and increasing number of comorbidities (IRR 1.09, 95%CI 1.03-1.15) were associated with increased risk of having more geriatric syndromes.²²

The presence of geriatric syndromes was significantly associated with increased LOS and institutionalization or change in residential care status

to a more dependent category. The factors most predictive of these outcomes were impaired pre-admission functional status in activities of daily living, recurrent falls, urinary incontinence and supported living arrangements. The geriatric syndromes appeared less important in predicting unplanned readmission and death.²³

Table (1) Results from Sequencing Studies.

Author and year	Sample	Geriatric syndromes	Key point
Pearl. L et al. 2009 ²⁰	Respondents in the 2004 wave of the HRS aged 65 and older	Self-reported presence of five index conditions (three chronic diseases (coronary artery disease, congestive heart failure, and diabetes mellitus) and two geriatric syndromes (urinary incontinence and injurious falls))	Five common conditions (3 chronic diseases, 2 geriatric syndromes) often co-occur in older adults,
Prabha. L 2011 ²¹	Five hundred seventy-seven general medical patients aged 70 and older admitted to the hospital.	syndromes in the pre-morbid (or pre-admission for falls), admission, and discharge periods; incidence of new syndromes at admission and discharge; and significant worsening of existing syndromes at admission and discharge.	Geriatric syndromes were highly prevalent. Many patients did not return to their pre-morbid function and acquired new syndromes.
Meredith 2015 ²²	G a cross-sectional study of HIV-infected adults age 50 and older	Geriatric syndromes including falls, urinary incontinence, functional impairment, frailty, sensory impairment, depression and cognitive impairment were measured in a cross-sectional study of HIV-infected adults age 50 and older	Geriatric syndromes are common in older HIV infected adults
Mahesan A 2007 ²³	A prospective longitudinal cohort study of patients aged 75 years admitted to the rapid assessment medical unit in a teaching hospital was carried out.	the association between the common geriatric syndromes and predefined adverse outcomes of hospitalization and to identify the most important independent predictors of adverse outcomes using information gained within 24 h of admission in older general medical patients.	The presence of geriatric syndromes in older general medical patients is an important determinant of adverse outcomes of hospitalization, particularly of LOS and admission to residential care. The predictors most useful for screening patients for these outcomes, within 24 h of admission, appear to be the presence of certain pre-existing geriatric syndromes before admission.

DISCUSSION:

This cross-sectional study examined the prevalence of the co-occurrence of three chronic diseases and two geriatric syndromes in the older adult population. These diseases and syndromes are important causes of morbidity in older adults and are targets of management guidelines and clinical quality measures. Previous studies have shown that co-occurring

chronic diseases are common in older adults.³ The current study, using nationally representative data, furthers these findings by demonstrating that the co-occurrence of chronic diseases with geriatric syndromes is also common. Especially remarkable is the finding that more than 25% of older adults with any one of the three chronic diseases also had at least one of the two geriatric syndromes.²⁰

This is the first study to report on the prevalence and the incidence of new and worsening of multiple geriatric syndromes in a single cohort of acutely ill general medical patients. The prevalence data are useful in highlighting the proportions of patients who experience multiple syndromes at three time periods. The finding that 95% of patients had at least one syndrome present in the premorbid period, with two-thirds experiencing between one and three syndromes, indicates that a majority of general medical patients aged 70 and older experience classic geriatric problems, especially bladder incontinence, receiving assistance with at least one ADL item, cognitive impairment, and falling before onset of illness. For a majority of syndromes present in the premorbid period, the greatest increase in prevalence occurred at admission and remained high at discharge. At discharge, more than half required assistance with bathing, and almost half required supervision or assistance with walking.²¹

The development of geriatric syndromes, multifactorial health conditions that impact morbidity, mortality and utilization of services, is one of the fundamental clinical manifestations of aging. A combination of risk factors for geriatric syndromes including psychosocial factors, such as social isolation and substance use, multimorbidity and polypharmacy as well as chronic inflammation, are common among older HIV-infected adults,⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ which has raised concern about how to decrease age related complications in this population.⁵ Based on these concerns, and findings from other studies identifying increased risk for frailty^{17,19} we undertook a comprehensive study of geriatric syndromes in middle-aged and older antiretroviral-treated adults. As hypothesized, we identified a frequent occurrence of geriatric syndromes, with pre-frailty, difficulty with IADLs, and cognitive impairment particularly common even amongst participants with well controlled HIV. A combination of both HIV-related factors (CD4 nadir) and non HIV-related factors (comorbidities, non-white race) were associated with increased risk of having more geriatric syndromes.²² This study confirms that the presence of geriatric syndromes in older general medical patients is significantly associated with adverse outcomes of hospitalization. Patients with a LOS ≥ 28 days and those who required admission to a residential care or moved to a more dependent facility were exclusively in the geriatric syndrome group. The geriatric syndromes were highly sensitive (100%) for screening patients for these outcomes, but they were only modestly specific – 62 and 67% for LOS and admission to residential aged care, respectively. As observed in other studies, this observation possibly

underscores the inherent difficulty in developing screening instruments with a high predictive accuracy to target high-risk patients in acute hospitals.^{10,21,22} One must acknowledge that multiple factors, including patient characteristics, disease severity, comorbid conditions, process of patient care and the social fabric of the patients, can all contribute to the various outcomes of hospitalization and, therefore, developing a screening tool with a high predictive value that encapsulates the interactions between these factors may not be easy [23].

CONCLUSION:

The results of this studies show the geriatric syndromes. On the basis of findings and results this review found urinary incontinence, injurious falls, functional impairment, frailty, sensory impairment, depression, cognitive impairment, significant worsening of existing syndromes at admission and discharge, and association between the common geriatric syndromes and predefined adverse outcomes of hospitalization, are most common geriatric syndromes Inouye.

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